

The Socio and Societal Responsibilities of the Islamic State: Analytical Study in the light of the Qur'an and Sunnah

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Abstract

The main aim of this research manuscript is to explore the socio and societal responsibility of the Islamic states. One of the basic responsibilities of the state, whether Islamic or non-Islamic, is to take the necessary steps for the betterment of society and society in practice. The primary responsibility of an Islamic state is to maintain an atmosphere of brotherhood and brotherhood among the people because when there is brotherhood and brotherhood then why would a Muslim deprive another Muslim of his rights. In the present era, all the forms of oppression, murder, vandalism and disenfranchisement that are common in the society are the result of turning away from the Islamic Brotherhood.

Introduction

The state is not only the goal of Islam but also the means of fulfilling the highest goals of Islam and a path which the Muslims themselves have been guided by God Almighty in his last book - the state is a necessary path without which Islam cannot exist among Muslims in its full form and spirit. Establishing a state to make Islam effective is a divine command, a prophetic tradition (2) and our responsibility. Allah has stated this in many places in the Qur'an It is also from the developmental philosophy of society. Allah says (interpretation of the meaning): "Verily, we sent Our Messengers with clear proofs, and We sent down with them the Book and the Balance of Justice, so that the people may stand up for justice." The philosophy of granting the Khilafah and the government is to establish the system of justice which is the divine intention that there should be justice among my creatures - justice is the divine intention and the purpose of Islam.

The responsibilities of the rulers in the Islamic State are such that after fulfilling every responsibility, the society automatically becomes calm. According to Islam, rulers are not rulers but servants of the nation. For them, power is not a source of luxury but a responsibility for which they are accountable to the Almighty before the people. Understand. They place the highest importance on the protection of religion and faith, life and property, honor and dignity of the people. In addition, there are many other responsibilities which we will explain in detail in this magazine. The first responsibility of any welfare state is to protect the life, property, honor and dignity of its people because unless there is peace and order within a nation and country then that country can never move on the path of development. Is. Therefore, an Islamic state has some basic responsibilities, the observance of which creates an atmosphere of peace and order and justice in the country. Some of these basic responsibilities are as follows.

1- Establishing an atmosphere of brotherhood

To keep the society free from all kinds of shortcomings in the rights of worship, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) promoted Islamic brotherhood among the brothers of faith.

Muslims are Brothers

Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said; Muslim is the brother of another Muslim.ⁱ The example of the believers' compassion for one another and their mutual relation and cooperation is like the relationship of the rest of the body with the rest of the body. Invites to be and it causes sleep deprivation and feverⁱⁱ. After his visit to Madinah, he uprooted all the roots that affect Islamic relations, thus emphasizing the need to avoid the vices of jealousy, envy, hatred, enmity, backbiting and gossip, which destroy mutual love. Do not be jealous of each other, do not break the relationship and become brothers, and do not stay away from your brother for more than three days.ⁱⁱⁱ

If these feelings of brotherhood and brotherhood spread in the Muslim society, then why would a Muslim deprive another Muslim of his rights, then oppression, aggression, murder and murder the forms of deprivation and deprivation of rights that are common in the society are the result of turning away from the

Islamic brotherhood. Therefore, it is necessary for the state to take steps at the governmental level to create an atmosphere of brotherhood and fraternity in the society.

2- Prevention of financial corruption

If dishonesty, betrayal and dishonesty are embedded in the financial system of a country then fair distribution of wealth is not possible. If government officials and officials get involved in corruption, the national treasury will be misused. Unauthorized people take everything from illegitimate sources, but the rightful ones are deprived. National income does not reach the people. If we look at the biography of the Holy Prophet (sws) for the solution of this serious problem, we find a very clear and effective code. The basis of your practical wisdom was the teachings of the Holy Qur'an in which we have been taught the distinction between halal and haraam and the scourge of haraam eating has been mentioned. At the same time, he presented a clear concept of honesty and dishonesty.

Along with clarifying the concept of halal and haraam through the Holy Quran, the Prophet (peace be upon him) emphasized the importance of trust and honesty in the practical life of the people. Explaining the importance of honesty. There is no faith in a person who does not have honesty.^{iv} He said that in which there is no trust, there is no faith. He who does not have his covenant has no religion. I swear by the entity in whose possession Muhammad's soul is, the religion of a servant will not be valid unless his language is correct and his language cannot be correct unless his heart is correct ... Whoever earns wealth from illicit means and spends from it will not be blessed. If he gives alms out of it, it will not be accepted. Whoever escapes from it will have the pleasure of traveling to Hell.^v One of the signs of the day of decision is that first of all the essence of trust will be lost from this Ummah.^{vi} The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) described betrayal of trust as a sign of hypocrisy.^{vii}

The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: You said. A believer can have every bad habit, but betrayal and lying cannot come into it. The Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: "Allah has placed the attribute of trust in the nature of mankind". no. A servant who has been martyred will be brought on the Day of Resurrection and will be asked to pay the trust (in which he has betrayed). He will say: O Allah! How can I bring it now, now the world is over? It will be said to take him to the Haviyya class of Hell. There the trustworthy object will come in front of him in its original state as an example, then he will recognize it by looking at it and will fall behind it to catch it till it catches it. He will carry it on his shoulders. But when he tries to get out of hell, the burden will fall on his shoulders. Then he will always fall behind it. Then he counted the ablutions, the prayers, the scales and many other things, and the hardest thing is the things of trust.^{viii}

In a hadith narrated from Ibn Umar, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) explained the importance of trust: When Allah wants to kill a slave, he removes the shame from it. When shame comes out of it, it always gets the wrath of Allah on it. When the wrath of Allah rests on him, the trust leaves his heart, and he always finds him a thief and a traitor. When he finds a thief and a traitor, mercy flows out of him. When mercy flows out of him, he will always find him cursed will When he was rejected and cursed all the time, the rope of Islam came out of his neck.^{ix}

3-To take all possible steps to solve the problems of the people

It is necessary for the state to be aware of the situation of the people, to do things for their benefit, to be kind and compassionate towards them, to forgive their mistakes, to decide with justice what kind of decision it deserves. What is mentioned about Islam? When he inspected the birds, he said, "I don't see what happened. He is missing."^x This verse proves that the Amir should be aware of the condition of his people. Ibn Umar (may Allah be pleased with him) narrated that the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) said: Every one of you is responsible and accountable for his responsibility. I think the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) also said that man is responsible for his father's wealth and is responsible for it.^{xi}

This is the reason why Hz. Omar Farooq seems so sensitive in the matter of informing his subjects that Dawood bin Ali says that Hz. Umar bin Khattab said: If even a young lamb (because of hunger) dies on the banks of the Euphrates, I fear that Allah will ask me about it.^{xii} Allama Shibli Nomani in Hz. Umar Farooq's biography "Al-Farooq" has a style that! Can you show such a ruler in the history of the whole world? Whose society is to have ten stitches in his shirt. With musk on his shoulder, poor women get water, sleep on the floor, walk in the bazaars, go wherever he goes and go alone Get oil on your body with your hands, Far from the court, not familiar with the name of Hasham and Khudam, and then it is horror and literature that Arabs and non-Arabs tremble at his name and whichever way you turn the earth trembles, Alexander and Timur thirty thousand. The army used to take them out in a saddle when they were terrified. In Omar Farooq's "Journey to Syria" there was nothing but riding camels.

4-Dealing with the people with patience and tolerance

One of the responsibilities of the Islamic State is that there should be courage, forbearance and tolerance within the Amir because three things are necessary for politics at all times: Hazrat Ali (RA) says about adoption. The good is not that you have more wealth and children but the good is that you have more knowledge, your morale is high.^{xiii}

Imam Tabari writes;It was reported to Umar Ibn Al-Khattab, may God be pleased with him, that a group of his subjects complained about his workers, so he commanded them to pay him. There is nothing dearer to God, nor dearer than a dream in front of and companionship.^{xiv} Hz. Muavia bin Ebi Sufyan said: “No one reaches the point of opinion, even though this patience overcomes his ignorance, and his patience overcomes his lust, and man reaches this point only through the power of patience.^{xv}Man cannot reach opinion until his patience overcomes his ignorance and his patience overcomes his lust, he can reach this place only through patience.

5-Protection of life and property of the people

Islam is the religion of respect for humanity. It not only teaches its followers peace and tolerance, tolerance and coexistence but also teaches respect for each other's beliefs and ideologies. It strictly forbids the killing of all human beings, not only Muslims but all races. The value and sanctity of a human life in Islam can be gauged from the fact that it has equated the killing of an individual without any reason with the killing of the whole of humanity. Allah Almighty has instructed in the Holy Qur'an regarding respect for humanity.

"Whoever kills a person without Qisas or mischief in the land (without punishment, unjustly) is as if he has killed all the people (of the society).^{xvi}In this blessed verse, the sanctity of human life is absolutely mentioned, in which men and women, young and old, rich and poor, even Muslims and non-Muslims Not customized. The point is that the Qur'an not only strictly forbids the killing of any human being without justification, but also makes it a murder of all humanity. As far as capital punishment is concerned in the law of Qisas etc., it is prescribed for the sanctity and protection of human blood.

The Holy Prophet (sww) has declared the sanctity of a believer to be more honorable than the sanctity of the Ka'bah. See the hadith narrated from Imam Ibn Majah:(It is narrated from Hz. Abdullah bin Umar (RA) that he saw the Holy Prophet (PBUH) circumambulating the Ka'bah and heard him say: (O Ka'bah!) How excellent you are and how sweet your fragrance By Allah, in whose hand is the soul of Muhammad! The sanctity of the believer's life and property is greater than your sanctity in the sight of Allah, and we have a good opinion of the believer,should keep.^{xvii}

6-Provide medical facilities for building a healthy society

The impact of climate change on the world and the discovery of new diseases is a disturbing situation. With the rising poverty and unemployment rates, people are suffering from mental and economic problems and there is a lack of proper medical treatment facilities. The plight of government hospitals is nothing short of traumatic for patients and their families. Treatment consists of two necessities, first medicine and second infrastructure, which together complement the public medical facilities. In times of global epidemics like Code 19 What bothered the people the most was the non-provision of medical facilities.

One of the major shortcomings was the emergence of infrastructure. Everyone was surprised and worried that he and his patient could not get treatment because the amount of infrastructure that the country needed was never paid attention to. What's more, governments today are still reluctant to accept that the basic need for medical care in a country or state There is a lack of infrastructure. But the fact is that there is a severe shortage of basic infrastructure in the medical field. This is the result of people dying without any treatment. Despite the existence of the National Pharmaceutical Pricing Authority, the world of medicine is that the price of a medicine that is available for Rs. 2,000 is Rs. 10,000. Acknowledges that there is a difference of up to two and a half hundred times between the actual cost and the MRP. Why never pay attention to this It has a price-controlling authority, yet it has so far taken only seven to eight hundred drugs under its purview. They can loot as they please.

Overall, if you look at the medical sector in the country, its condition is very bad. Not all medical facilities, from government hospitals to private ones, exist in the first place and where there are, the looting is so high that patients die before physical death. Therefore, in order to provide affordable medical services, it is necessary for the government to first fix the prices of all medicines through the pricing authority so that the patients can be saved from being robbed by the pharmaceutical companies and their entire gang. The government does not solve the problem of pricing, until then the people in the country cannot get cheap treatment.

Which is its fundamental right and the basic duty of the state. It should also fix the prices of pathological check-ups, surgeries and hospital admissions and beds so that the people have to face minimum difficulties in bad days. Central and state governments have launched various schemes for free and cheap treatment which People are benefiting from this but this level is insufficient as such schemes are able to bring very few people under its purview whereas if only medicines are made cheaper then looting in the name of medicine should be stopped.So the benefits will be much wider. Now is the time for governments to amend pricing rules and regulations to force companies to write down the actual price of medicines and it is the responsibility of the government to do its duty. Therefore, the central and state governments need to pay special attention to this so that the people can get some relief.

7- Promoting education and training

The importance of education and training can be gauged from the fact that the Prophet Abraham (peace be upon him) prayed to God to send a messenger to describe him as a prophet who teaches and teaches people the Book. (And our Lord! Send among them a Messenger from among them, who shall recite to them Thy communications before them, and teach them the Book and wisdom, and purify them.^{xviii} Also, Allah Almighty, while bestowing blessings on the believers, said: I have sent among you a Messenger whose duties include education and training. Indeed, Allah has been gracious to the believers that He has sent among them a Messenger from among them who recites to them the communications of Allah and purifies them and teaches them the Book and wisdom. Before, they were in open error.^{xix}

The Holy Prophet also stated his position, That I have been sent as a teacher, educator and spoke.^{xx} Despite the great need for importance of education and training, very little attention is being paid to education and training in our country. The budget allocates much less to education than to defense and other expenditures, and that too is often spent on administrative expenses and other matters instead of education. It is the right and responsibility of the government. If you know the children of the book support. Therefore, the Prophet (peace and blessings of Allah be upon him) arranged for the children of the Ansar to be taught writing.^{xxi}

One of the difficulties in getting education is that our curriculum is not in the mother tongue and national language, but more emphasis is given on English, even if a person wants to do MA, M.Phil etc. in Urdu, Pashto, Islamic studies or any other subject. It is necessary to go through difficult stages, but more questions will be related to English than the relevant subject. There is no difference between English as a subject and English as a medium of instruction. Not hidden from the educator, the student can express his / her conscience in his / her mother tongue. He cannot do it in non-mother tongue at all. Secondly, very few people are proficient in non-mother tongue. Otherwise, ordinary people continue to work with limited vocabulary. The Sunnah of God is that Allah Almighty sent every nation as a messenger and then in their language so that they could understand the nation in their language. That is, people adopt the method as their kings.^{xxii}

That is, when the head of the household is keen to play the drums, the rest of the household must be in the habit of dancing.^{xxiii} Therefore, the government of the day and the Department of Education will promote ignorance and obscenity in the name of education and will not remove the existing barriers and obstacles in the field of education and training. Now, what are the responsibilities of the government and the education department, the fulfillment of which is to make up for the lack of knowledge and lack of training, which are briefly written below.

From an Islamic point of view, Arabs and non-Arabs alike are rich and poor in the acquisition of knowledge. The children do not achieve the desired goals, and because of this the children fall prey to the feeling of inferiority and give up the pursuit of knowledge. This is the teaching of Islam to provide free and impartial education to the children of the poor by bearing the educational expenses like the children of, these are Islamic teachings.

One of the important things to address the lack of education and training that can be an arrow to save our young generation from misguidance is to promote religious education and values in schools, colleges and universities, our religion, Islam. The name itself is education and training, so unless religious literature is made an important part of the curriculum and the youth are made aware of the educational and training achievements of their predecessors, these architects of the nation will continue to wander like this, Muslims who are not Living in Islamic countries, they resort to religion to save their children from going astray, which is a hundred percent successful experience.

Conclusion

One of the basic responsibilities of the state, whether Islamic or non-Islamic, is to take the necessary steps for the betterment of society and society in practice. Because if any state tries to fulfill its responsibilities, then the welfare and peace in the society is automatically created within the state. In an Islamic state, the rulers are in fact the servants of the nation and they try to carry out the functions of the state as their responsibility. In their responsibilities, they place the highest importance on the protection of religion, faith, life and property, honor and dignity of the people. Because unless there is peace and order within a nation and a country, that country can never be on the path of development. Therefore, in the Qur'an and Hadith, there is a strong emphasis on fulfilling the social and societal responsibilities of the Islamic State in a cordial manner, which we have already discussed. So, no one will be able to infringe on anyone's rights. If the state fulfills its responsibility to protect the lives and property of the people in the society, then there will be no killing in the society. Ensure the safety of property. The value and sanctity of a human life in Islam can be gauged from the fact that it has equated the killing of an individual without any reason with the killing of the whole of humanity. Lack of education and training is one of the main reasons for creating an atmosphere of chaos, sedition, oppression and injustice in any nation and country. Although education is the right of every child and is the responsibility of the government, if the children are educated then there will be peace and order in the society. Therefore, it is important for the ruler to spare no effort in meeting the basic needs of the society. So that a better society can last forever.

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